

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN OPTIMIZATION APPROACH TO THE PRELIMINARY DESIGN OF A SOLAR THERMAL THRUSTER FOR THE GREEN SWAP PROJECT

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ABSTRACT:

The Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) methodology provides a systematic framework for designing complex engineering systems involving interacting disciplines and conflicting objectives. Although widely used in aeronautics, its application to spacecraft propulsion remains limited. This paper presents the formulation and implementation of an MDO framework for the preliminary design of a Solar Thermal Thruster developed for auxiliary propulsion within the Green SWaP project.

The system delivers 1 N of vacuum thrust, throttleable from 30% to 120%, with a minimum specific impulse of 500 s using gaseous hydrogen. The objective is to minimize overall thruster length while meeting thrust and performance requirements under varying orbital conditions.

The architecture optimizes nozzle and heat exchanger dimensions that guarantee the required performance within the operating conditions. By coupling thermal and fluid-dynamic analyses, the framework captures trade-offs between performance and compactness. Results highlight MDO's value in supporting informed, quantitatively justified early-stage design decisions.

NOMENCLATURE:

T_{wall}	[K]	HEX wall temperature
$T_m(L)$	[K]	medium temperature at L position
$T_{m,in}$	[K]	medium temperature at HEX inlet
P	[m]	HEX channel perimeter
L	[m]	HEX channel length
\dot{m}	[kg/s]	mass flow
c_p	[J/kg K]	specific heat at constant pressure
h	[W/m ² K]	convective heat coefficient
Nu	[-]	Nusselt number
k_f	[W/m K]	fluid thermal conductivity
f	[-]	friction factor
Re	[-]	Reynolds number

Pr	[-]	Prandtl number
v_2	[m/s]	nozzle exit velocity
γ	[-]	specific heat ratio
R	[J/kg K]	mass specific gas constant
T_1	[K]	temperature upstream the nozzle
p_1	[Pa]	pressure upstream the nozzle
p_2	[Pa]	pressure at nozzle exit
A_t	[m ²]	nozzle throat area
A_2	[m ²]	nozzle exit area
I_{sp}	[s]	specific impulse
g_0	[m/s ²]	standard gravity
F	[N]	thrust
p_3	[Pa]	ambient pressure

1. INTRODUCTION

Space propulsion systems are essential for spacecraft operations, supporting activities such as orbital transfers, attitude regulation, station-keeping, and other critical manoeuvres. As mission objectives have become increasingly sophisticated and diverse, the demand for propulsion technologies with enhanced and versatile capabilities has grown significantly. This evolution has led to the emergence of innovative solutions designed to achieve greater performance, higher efficiency, and, in some cases, reduced overall costs.

The Green SWaP project, an EU/EIC Pathfinder initiative, focuses on advancing the key technologies required for water-based propulsion through a novel strategy that differs from previous approaches. Green SWaP aims to develop and validate technologies that harness solar energy to produce a dual-propellant combination from water: hydrogen peroxide and hydrogen. These substances form the basis of two innovative propulsion concepts. The first is a high-thrust bipropellant engine that uses concentrated hydrogen peroxide together with gaseous hydrogen. The second is a low-thrust solar thermal propulsion system powered by gaseous hydrogen, designed to provide an efficient and sustainable option for extended missions or precision manoeuvring tasks ([1], [2]).

The Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) concept was

introduced in the 1950s, initially as an upper-stage engine. The key feature of this technology is the decoupling of the propellant from the energy source used for propulsion, relying on an external energy source. Unlike chemical propulsion systems, where the energy is intrinsically linked to the propellants and therefore limited by them, and unlike electrical propulsion systems, where the energy source is stored within the spacecraft's electrical components, the energy source for a solar thermal thruster is sunlight, which is external to the spacecraft. Additionally, hydrogen is theoretically the most suitable propellant for this type of system in terms of specific impulse. Owing to its low molar mass, specific impulses of up to 1100 s can theoretically be achieved [3].

The STT propulsion system comprises three main components: the solar concentrator, the light absorber/heat exchanger (HEX), and the nozzle. A schematic representation of the system is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: STT scheme [4]

The solar concentrator is typically a concave reflecting surface (or an array of surfaces) that concentrates incident sunlight. The absorber/heat exchanger receives solar radiation, converts it into heat, and transfers this heat to the propellant. The nozzle, as in more conventional propulsion concepts, accelerates the heated propellant, converting its thermal energy into kinetic energy to generate thrust.

The first STT prototypes were conceived as innovative upper-stage engines [5]. Still, the concept was later set aside due to challenges associated with the large solar concentrators required and the handling of liquid hydrogen. Subsequent research focused on applying this concept to smaller thrusters ([6], [7], [8]) and on developing systems capable of withstanding the high temperatures required for high specific impulse. For the Green SWaP application, hydrogen storage issues are mitigated through in-orbit propellant production. Additionally, a solution proposed by Kennedy [6], which connects smaller concentrators to the absorber via optical fibres, brings STT technology closer to practical flight applications. Therefore, this technology is considered highly suitable for auxiliary propulsion purposes. Green SWaP aims to reach Technology Readiness Level 4 (TRL 4) with a prototype for this application.

To meet the requirements for attitude control and the precise in-orbit maneuvers foreseen, and to justify the implementation of this technology for

such purposes, the thruster must provide a minimum specific impulse of 500 s. This requirement corresponds to a minimum propellant temperature of approximately 1300 K. The thrust must also be throttleable between 0.3 N and 1.2 N, based on mission requirements [9].

While thrust is primarily regulated by the chamber pressure, which can be directly controlled via a pressure regulator, the propellant temperature is directly related to the wall temperature of the HEX and therefore to the level of solar radiation responsible for heating the HEX.

The objective of the HEX is to heat the propellant sufficiently to achieve the minimum specific impulse requirement. As mentioned, the minimum wall temperature is approximately 1300 K, while the system may be designed to operate at the highest temperature permitted by the materials. In this case, the wall temperature is not a fixed value but rather depends on the satellite's environmental and operational conditions. Therefore, it is treated in this work as an external parameter influencing performance that the designer must account for.

Given the required thrust range and the wide range of HEX wall temperatures over which the thruster can operate, a method to evaluate the performance of preliminary thruster designs is necessary.

Furthermore, since the thruster will be used on a satellite, it is essential to minimize its volume, as this directly reduces the overall subsystem mass by reducing the material required for components and insulation. A more compact design also simplifies integration within the spacecraft.

In addition, both the project and the propulsion system are currently at low TRL and in early design phases. These stages are characterized by frequent and rapid changes in requirements and boundary conditions, which significantly impact the thruster design and require multiple iterative modifications.

The design and corresponding optimization efforts reported in this paper focus on the HEX fluidic path and nozzle, whereas light collection and concentration, as well as absorber-cavity design, are outside the current scope of work.

1.1. Classic design approach

The first design approach followed for the preliminary design of the STT is the classical one, in which the thruster is divided into its two main components: the nozzle and the HEX. The nozzle is designed first, and the HEX is subsequently designed based on the operating conditions defined by the nozzle. As previously stated, the design focuses only on the fluidic path of the HEX and the nozzle. At Preliminary Design Review (PDR) level, fixed geometries were selected for both components: the HEX is represented as a circular tube with uniform wall temperature and constant diameter, while the nozzle has a convergent-divergent conical geometry with a fixed convergent semi-angle of 30° and a divergent semi-angle of 15°.

For the mathematical modelling of the HEX, the simplified correlations reported in Eqs. 1–6 ([10]) are used to relate the exit temperature of the fluid to the flow regime, wall temperature, and tube length. The assumptions include flow in a circular tube with constant diameter and surface roughness, uniform wall temperature, and negligible pressure drop across the HEX.

$$\frac{T_{wall} - T_m(L)}{T_{wall} - T_{m, in}} = e^{-\frac{PL}{\dot{m} c_p} h} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$Nu \equiv \frac{hL}{k_f} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$Nu = 3.66 \quad (\text{laminar}) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$Nu = \frac{\left(\frac{f}{8}\right) (Re - 1000) Pr}{1 + 12.7 \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^{1/2} (Pr^{2/3} - 1)} \quad (\text{turbulent}) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$f = \frac{64}{Re} \quad (\text{laminar}) \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$f = (0.790 \ln Re - 1.64)^{-2} \quad (\text{turbulent}) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

For the nozzle modelling, ideal rocket theory is applied using the standard equations for thrust, specific impulse, mass flow rate, expansion ratio, exit velocity and throat/exit nozzle area ratio as reported in Eqs. 7–11 ([11]).

$$v_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{\gamma-1} R T_1 \left[1 - \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}}\right]} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\dot{m} = A_t p_1 \gamma \frac{\sqrt{\left[\frac{2}{\gamma+1}\right]^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}}}{\sqrt{\gamma R T_1}} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\frac{A_t}{A_2} = \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma-1}} \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}}\right]} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$I_{sp} = \frac{F}{\dot{m} g_0} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$F = \dot{m} v_2 + (p_2 - p_3) A_2 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

The requirements define the thrust and specific impulse of the thruster, while orbital operating conditions and material melting points impose limits on the HEX wall temperature. All other design parameters are treated as free variables. For the HEX, the channel length and internal diameter influence the final temperature of the propellant upstream of the nozzle. For the nozzle, the throat area, expansion ratio, and upstream chamber pressure influence the mass flow rate and generated thrust.

A summary of the design parameters for the thruster is reported in Tab. 1.

Table 1: thruster design parameters

Parameter	Constrained or free
Nozzle throat area	Free parameter
Temperature upstream of the nozzle	Linked to HEX length and wall temperature
Exit pressure	Free parameter but linked to the expansion ratio
Pressure upstream of the nozzle	Free parameter
Nozzle exit area	Free parameter but linked to the expansion ratio
Wall temperature	Varying depending on operating conditions
Inlet fluid temperature	Fixed
HEX channel length	Free parameter
Mass flow HEX	Depending on the nozzle design and thrust required
HEX channel diameter	Free parameter

The first component to be designed independently is the nozzle. For the initial iteration, the fluid temperature upstream of the nozzle is assumed to be 3000 K. This assumption is based on the hypothesis that the thruster is made of tungsten and that the system heats the material close to its maximum allowable temperature in order to provide a thermal margin when sunlight is not available. During such periods, the thruster temperature would decrease, but the margin will allow the temperature to stay above 1300 K, and consequently, the specific impulse would still remain above the required 500 s.

Given the required thrust range, the most critical design decision concerns the chamber pressure. A higher chamber pressure allows for a smaller nozzle, but it also affects the lifetime of the thruster (due to higher tank pressures), as well as the mass of the tubing and tanks, and the required manufacturing precision.

The selected design point corresponds to a thrust of 0.3 N at a chamber pressure of 1.8 bar(a). The choice of this pressure is based on the designer's decision of having a nozzle that remains choked under an external pressure of 1 bar(a). Since the nozzle must provide thrust between 0.3 N and 1.2 N, the design point was selected at the minimum thrust level, with higher thrust values obtained by increasing the chamber pressure. Therefore, the lower pressure boundary condition of 1.8 bar(a) is automatically satisfied in the thrust range required. An extensive parametric study was performed to evaluate the effects of throat area, expansion ratio, chamber pressure, and fluid temperature in order to obtain a throat diameter larger than 0.5 mm, thereby simplifying manufacturing. The final nozzle

geometry features a throat diameter of approximately 1.1 mm and an expansion ratio of 36. The design of the nozzle was based on these parametric studies, and the final values were selected considering operational requirements (pressure range needed to obtain the required thrust range), manufacturing constraints (dimensions that allow straightforward fabrication), and volume considerations (reducing the dimensions of the thruster).

Once the geometric parameters of the nozzle are fixed, the mass flow rate is calculated for different upstream fluid temperatures and thrust levels, corresponding to different chamber pressures. This mass flow rate is then used as an input for the HEX design. Another extensive parametric study is conducted to determine the optimal channel diameter and tube length.

Since the HEX wall temperature varies during orbital operation, the objective of the HEX design is to bring the propellant temperature as close as possible to the varying wall temperature across the full required mass flow range. The final HEX design features a channel diameter of 1.25 mm and a tube length of approximately 28 cm.

The performance of the thruster (thrust and specific impulse) at varying chamber pressures and HEX wall temperatures is reported in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: performance of the thruster designed with the classic approach

During the design process, it becomes evident that design choices for the nozzle influence the performance of the HEX, and vice versa. To properly account for this interaction, both components should ideally be designed simultaneously. However, given the varying operating conditions and the coupling between the components, the number of iterations required becomes substantial, leading to long design times. In addition, initial assumptions are necessary to start the design process, meaning that many design choices and the direction of the iterative process are guided primarily by engineering experience.

Moreover, given the early development stage of both the project and the STT technology, requirements and boundary conditions may change

rapidly and frequently. As a result, lengthy and repetitive design iterations would need to be repeated every time a modification occurs.

Despite the significant simplifications introduced by assuming a conical nozzle with a fixed aperture and a simplified HEX model, selecting the design parameters remains challenging due to the virtually infinite number of parameter combinations that satisfy the requirements. Furthermore, the classical approach effectively designs one component at a time, while the other component's design becomes a consequence of the initial design choices.

Given the aforementioned limitations of the classical approach, an alternative design methodology should be considered to enable faster design iterations and to explicitly account for the interaction between the thruster components.

2. MDO METHOD

The Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) methodology provides a more formalized approach to complex system design compared with traditional design methods, which typically rely on iterative procedures in which an initial design is analysed and progressively adapted to meet requirements. The objective of MDO is achieved by applying numerical optimization techniques to the multidisciplinary design process.

Complex systems are generally too intricate for a single designer to fully comprehend all associated details and interactions. A key aspect of this complexity is the inherently multidisciplinary nature of the design process. The multidisciplinary approach addresses this complexity by dividing a large system into smaller, more manageable subsystems, referred to as disciplines, thereby enabling designers to better manage and structure the overall design task.

These disciplines, representing components or analytical aspects of the final design object, are often mutually dependent. As a result, substantial amounts of information must be exchanged among them. Effective coordination is therefore required to guide the process toward convergence. Managing this information flow is further complicated by the inherently iterative nature of the design process.

The goal of MDO is to provide a structured framework that formalizes the multidisciplinary design process, making it suitable for numerical optimization. The use of numerical optimization techniques is expected to significantly improve the efficiency and robustness of the design process. Moreover, it helps overcome limitations associated with traditional sequential design approaches [12]. MDO techniques are well established in the aeronautical research field, particularly in the design of advanced aircraft concepts. In such applications, multiple disciplines (such as structural engineering, aerodynamics, and propulsion) are strongly coupled, and decisions made within one discipline directly influence the others. State-of-the-art wing design methodologies, for example, integrate

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Finite Element Method (FEM) analyses to achieve optimized advanced design concepts ([13]). Despite its application in the aeronautical field, the use of MDO architecture and methods remains limited in the space propulsion field. At the moment that this paper is written, only one publication on the application of the MDO for a conceptual design trade-off of a bipropellant is present [14], while none can be found for propulsion components design. MDO optimization is mostly used in the space sector to optimize the entire satellite system for preliminary design of subsystems ([15], [16]).

In addition to its multidisciplinary nature, the second fundamental pillar of MDO is optimization. Optimization can be defined as the search for the best possible solution to a given problem, where the definition of “best” depends on the specific objectives. In MDO, numerical optimization is employed, where the quality of a solution is quantified through one or more objective (or goal) functions.

A solution is typically represented by a design vector containing the design variables. An optimizer is a mathematical algorithm that systematically explores the design space, the set of all possible design configurations, in a manner that is significantly more efficient than exhaustively evaluating every possible combination.

The intended outcome of applying numerical optimization within a structured multidisciplinary framework is to extract greater multidisciplinary insight from each evaluated design option, particularly during the early stages of a project when design freedom is highest. In this sense, MDO can be viewed as a tool for exploring the design space and supporting system-level decision-making during the conceptual phase through quantitative analysis.

Ideally, although the conceptual phase may require more time and computational effort, the subsequent design phases become shorter and more streamlined. Preliminary designs developed through MDO are generally less prone to major corrections or redesigns. This is because MDO allows greater design freedom to be maintained for a longer period, reducing the need for premature decisions that would otherwise constrain or freeze the design. Figure 3 graphically illustrates the objective of an MDO approach applied to complex system design.

Figure 3: MDO aims for design [17]

A common systems engineering tool used to visualize interactions and dependencies among elements of a complex system is the Design Structure Matrix (DSM). An example is shown in Fig. 4 (where Disc. stands for “discipline”).

Figure 4: general DSM

In a DSM, the upper-right corner typically represents outputs from elements that are used by other elements, while the lower-left corner represents input parameters required by each element. The presence of a mark (e.g., a black dot) indicates a dependency between two elements. However, the information conveyed by a DSM is limited to the existence of links between elements. To enhance its informative value, the graphical representation can be extended by scaling the marks according to the amount of data exchanged or by explicitly listing the exchanged variables, as in Fig 5.

While the DSM captures the interaction links between system elements, it does not inherently ensure consistency between the inputs and outputs of each discipline during analysis. To achieve this consistency, a coordinating mechanism is required. This coordinator ensures that, during iterative analysis, the outputs and inputs of all elements remain consistent. When this coordinating function is integrated into the DSM framework, the result is a Multidisciplinary Design Analysis (MDA) scheme, illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: MDA scheme

The MDA performs the iterative coordination among disciplines. Each discipline requires input data, which may include fixed design parameters or initialized values for the iterative process. The MDA operates as a conventional iterative method, ensuring that the coupled analyses converge to a consistent solution.

A more advanced formalization of the DSM was

proposed by Martins and Lambe [18] in the form of the Extended Design Structure Matrix (XDSM). The XDSM not only represents data exchanges between elements but also illustrates the process sequence by including the order in which elements are executed and the direction of data flow. An example of an XDSM is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: XDSM for a MDA three discipline coupled system [19]

Up to this point, the formalization of complex systems has been described without explicitly incorporating optimization. The XDSM was specifically developed to formalize optimization problems within a multidisciplinary framework. In a typical optimization algorithm, the design variables are assembled into a design vector, which the optimizer modifies in order to minimize (or maximize) an objective function while satisfying the constraints imposed by the problem. An XDSM representation of an optimization problem is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: XDSM for optimization problems [19]

For a multidisciplinary design optimization problem, the XDSM representations of the multidisciplinary analysis and the optimization process can be unified into a single framework, as illustrated in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: XDSM for MDO [19]

The architecture shown corresponds to a Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF) formulation. In this architecture, the optimizer modifies the design

vector. For each candidate design, the MDA coordinator iterates among the disciplinary analyses to ensure that the system-level solution is feasible and internally consistent. Using the results of the MDA, the optimizer evaluates the objective function and verifies that all constraints are satisfied. This process is repeated iteratively until the objective function is minimized or maximized according to the problem definition.

The final result is an optimized design vector containing the optimal set of design variables.

The MDO problem, as represented by the XDSM framework, embodies a modern approach to multidisciplinary design, where design parameters are optimized within predefined bounds in order to maximize or minimize an objective function while satisfying the constraints imposed by the system requirements.

3. MDO ARCHITECTURE FOR THE STT

Based on the MDO theory described in the previous chapter, the STT design was implemented at PDR level in order to properly manage the interaction between components, account for operational constraints, and reduce the time required for design iterations.

For a space propulsion thruster, mass and volume are two parameters that are desirable to minimize. However, minimizing the mass would require a more advanced analysis that accounts for the full three-dimensional geometry of the thruster and the insulation system. At the current stage, directly correlating mass with the prototype model was considered excessively complex for a PDR-level study.

Therefore, the selected objective function is the minimization of the total thruster length, defined as the sum of the HEX tube length and the axial length of the nozzle. Minimizing the overall length is expected to indirectly reduce both the final mass and the volume of the prototype.

The XDSM representing the MDO architecture for the STT design is shown in Fig. 9.

The MDO architecture reflects the overall design process of the thruster. During each iteration, the optimizer modifies the design parameters (called design vector) of the components. Based on these parameters, the Multidisciplinary Design Analysis (MDA) calculates the thruster performance over the full required thrust range and for different HEX wall temperatures, ensuring that the design remains internally consistent. The resulting performance and design parameters are then compared against the imposed constraints. The optimizer subsequently generates a new set of design parameters to identify the configuration that minimizes the objective function while satisfying all constraints.

The design vector consists of the following parameters:

- HEX channel length
- HEX channel diameter
- Nozzle expansion ratio

- Nozzle throat diameter

Boundary limits are imposed on selected design variables. The nozzle throat diameter must be greater than 0.5 mm, while the HEX channel length and nozzle expansion ratio have a lower bound of zero. No lower bound is imposed on the HEX channel diameter, since a constraint directly relates it to the nozzle throat diameter. Similarly, no upper bounds are imposed on the channel length, channel diameter, expansion ratio, or nozzle throat diameter to avoid unnecessarily restriction to the optimizer. The minimum throat diameter bound is set to facilitate easier and less expensive manufacturing. Within these bounds, the optimizer modifies the design variables to identify the optimal combination that minimizes the total thruster length.

For each optimization iteration, the design vector is passed to the Multidisciplinary Design Analysis (MDA) system, which consists of three main disciplinary blocks in the STT case:

- Nozzle
- HEX
- Off-design performance

Each discipline uses the same mathematical models adopted in the classical design approach ([10], [11]).

For each candidate design generated during the optimization process, the thruster performance is evaluated across the entire required thrust range and for different HEX wall temperatures.

Once the performance is calculated, the results are compared against the constraints defined for the problem.

1. HEX channel diameter constraint.

The HEX channel area must be at least 1.5 times the nozzle throat area. This constraint prevents flow choking within the HEX. The value of 1.5 is somewhat arbitrary but is considered sufficient, as typical solid rocket motors use values of port/throat area ratio around 2-3 [11];

2. Choked nozzle condition.

The nozzle must operate under choked flow conditions. Therefore, the chamber pressure must exceed the minimum value determined by the specific heat ratio and the exit pressure ([11]);

3. Maximum chamber pressure allowed.

For each iteration, the geometry of the thruster is fixed by the optimizer, while the HEX wall temperature is treated as an external parameter. Under these conditions, the thruster must deliver thrust between 0.3 N and 1.2 N, and the only variable parameter used to achieve this range is the chamber pressure. The maximum allowable chamber pressure during operation is limited to 7 bar(a), which therefore constrains the pressure required to achieve the maximum thrust. This upper limit, although defined by the designer and somewhat arbitrary, is chosen to promote longer operational lifetime and to limit structural mass;

4. Minimum specific impulse requirement

Across the entire operational range, corresponding to different chamber pressures, mass flow rates and wall temperature, the specific impulse must always remain above 500 s.

For each design candidate, the code evaluates compliance with these constraints by combining the design vector variables (modified by the optimizer) with external parameters such as HEX wall temperature, propellant properties, and thrust range, which are defined by the designer and remain fixed during the optimization process.

Figure 9: XDSM for STT

4. RESULTS FOR THE STT PDR

The MDO architecture described above was implemented in a MATLAB script. The optimizer used is the function *fmincon*, which employs a gradient-based algorithm and is suitable for constrained optimization problems.

The optimized design parameters are reported in Tab. 2 and compared with the values obtained using the classical design approach. Although no rigorous numerical optimization is performed in the classical approach, the design is based on extensive parametric studies carried out on each component in an iterative manner. As explained in the dedicated chapter, the final design results from the designer's choices and expertise in interpreting the parametric analyses and guiding the iterative process.

Table 2: comparison between classic design approach results and MDO design results

	Classic design approach	MDO approach
Length HEX	28 cm	9.61 cm
Channel diameter HEX	1.25 mm	1.3674 mm
Nozzle throat diameter	1.1 mm	1.1165 mm
Nozzle expansion ratio	36	72.6204

The performances of the thruster (thrust and specific impulse) designed based on the MDO results at the varying chamber pressure and HEX wall temperature are reported in Fig 10.

Figure 10: performance of the thruster designed with MDO method

The optimization process required approximately 30 minutes on a standard laptop (HP EliteBook 6). A known limitation of gradient-based optimization methods is the potential convergence to a local minimum rather than the global minimum. To mitigate this issue, the optimization was performed using multiple initial starting points for the design vector. Regardless of the initial values, the optimizer

consistently converged to the same design solution reported in Table 2.

Although there is no formal mathematical proof that the obtained solution corresponds to the global minimum, the consistent convergence from different initial conditions provides strong confidence in the optimality of the result. It is also worth noting that even convergence to a local minimum generally represents an improvement over an initial, non-optimized design configuration.

5. COMMENTS ON THE RESULTS

The results obtained confirm that MDO architectures can be effectively applied to the design of space propulsion thrusters. In the case of the STT, the results highlight the following main advantages:

- The use of numerical optimization methods enables the identification of an optimal design point that would be extremely difficult to achieve without computational support. In this case, the total length of the thruster was reduced by approximately one-third compared with the classical approach (whose goodness is more linked to the experience of the designer);
- It is also worth noting that the nozzle designed using the classical approach (being the first component designed in that process) has smaller overall dimensions compared to the design obtained with the MDO method. This result is a direct consequence of the parametric study performed by the designer on the first component. In contrast, the nozzle obtained through the MDO process is larger, but it enables the overall thruster to be smaller. This highlights one of the main strengths of the MDO approach: the optimization of the entire system rather than of individual components;
- The multidisciplinary (multi-component) nature of the system is inherently captured within the script, and multiple off-design constraints are automatically verified during the optimization process;
- The speed of the design process is remarkable: an optimized configuration can be generated in approximately 30 minutes.

Once the MDO architecture is implemented in code, it becomes a flexible and efficient design tool for the thruster. A major advantage is that all operational constraints and component interface conditions are embedded within the framework. As a result, the inherently iterative nature of the design process is handled automatically by the computational system rather than manually by the designer.

In a design environment characterized by significant

freedom and a large number of possible parameter combinations, the MDO methodology guides the design toward an optimal solution using rigorous mathematical methods. The information generated through this process is particularly valuable during preliminary design phases or for low TRL technologies, where detailed system knowledge is still limited.

Precisely because system knowledge is limited at these early stages, the MDO architecture can also be used as a tool for exploring the design space. By modifying or relaxing constraint values, the designer can study how operational limits influence the resulting configuration and gain insight into system sensitivities. The exploration of the design space is outside the scope of this paper and will be addressed in future work as a continuation of the present study.

Furthermore, if the thruster is intended for a mission or application that is still under development, requirements may change rapidly. Once the MDO architecture has been established, re-design in response to updated requirements requires only the time needed to re-run the optimization process (approximately 30 minutes in this case).

Independent of the specific STT application, the developed architecture can be extended to the design of other types of space propulsion systems. The disciplinary blocks are based on general mathematical models of a nozzle and a heat exchanger. In the STT case, the specific application primarily affects the constraints and external conditions within which the optimizer operates. By modifying the external environment and constraint definitions, the same architecture could be adapted to represent other propulsion concepts, such as cold gas thrusters or resistojets.

Therefore, the MDO framework can also be used to compare different thruster types at the PDR level, or to evaluate the use of different propellants, ensuring that each concept is analyzed at or near its optimized configuration. This capability can significantly support early-stage trade-off analyses between competing propulsion technologies during satellite or mission design.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE CREATED MDO ARCHITECTURE AND FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

The MDA system is based on simplified mathematical models, which inherently include assumptions and approximations. Consequently, the resulting design reflects the limitations of these simplified models and may differ from the performance of real hardware.

For example, in the nozzle model, frictional effects are neglected. However, in small nozzles such as those considered for the STT, boundary layer displacement thickness and viscous losses can play a significant role, potentially influencing performance and therefore the optimal design. At the PDR level, the use of simplified models is

acceptable, and the optimized design can be considered valid within this modelling framework. Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize that the optimizer operates strictly on the numerical models provided; therefore, the quality of the result is directly dependent on the fidelity of these models.

To use the MDO architecture as a truly effective design tool, the mathematical models of each component should represent the physical phenomena as accurately as possible. When higher-fidelity models are implemented, the optimizer can identify solutions that more closely reflect real-world performance. For this reason, the implementation of boundary layer effects, as well as other relevant physical phenomena, will be considered in the future. Moreover, once developed, such realistic disciplinary blocks can be reused for multiple systems and technologies, increasing the long-term value of the MDO framework.

Another limitation of the current architecture lies in the intrinsic nature of numerical optimization. The optimizer produces continuous numerical values, whereas manufacturing processes cannot guarantee infinite precision. As a result, the exact optimized parameter values cannot always be manufactured directly. If MDO is applied to prototype development, manufacturing tolerances and discretization constraints should be explicitly integrated into the optimization framework.

The current model also has limitations in terms of geometric representation and the number of components considered. Additional design variables could be introduced to expand the optimizer's scope and explore a broader design space. Similarly, more advanced component models could be implemented to enable optimization of more complex geometries.

At present, only the HEX and the nozzle are included in the MDO architecture. Future developments could incorporate additional elements, such as the absorption cavity or even the entire propulsion system, in order to fully exploit the multidisciplinary optimization capabilities of the MDO framework, particularly if the objective of the design shifts from the thruster alone to the entire propulsion subsystem. Although this would increase the computational time required for optimization due to the larger number of design parameters, expanding the system boundary would reduce the number of externally imposed constraints and allow the optimizer to define a larger set of parameters, ultimately leading to a more globally optimized propulsion system design.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the development and application of a Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) framework for the preliminary design of a Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) within the Green SWaP project. The objective was to overcome the limitations of classical sequential

design approaches by explicitly accounting for the strong coupling between the nozzle and heat exchanger (HEX), as well as the operational constraints imposed by mission requirements and operational conditions.

The comparison between the classical design methodology and the MDO-based approach demonstrates the clear advantages of formalized multidisciplinary optimization. While the classical approach requires extensive manual iterations and relies heavily on engineering intuition, the MDO framework embeds disciplinary interactions, off-design conditions, and system constraints directly within the optimization loop. This enables systematic exploration of the design space and leads to a significantly more efficient design process.

The optimized STT configuration satisfies the required thrust range (0.3 - 1.2 N), guarantees a minimum specific impulse of 500 s at HEX wall temperatures above 1300 K, and achieves a substantial reduction in overall thruster length compared with the initial classical design. The optimization process, implemented in MATLAB using a gradient-based constrained algorithm, demonstrated rapid convergence and robust behavior with respect to different initial conditions.

Beyond the specific numerical results, the main contribution of this work lies in demonstrating that MDO methodologies can be effectively transferred to the design of space propulsion thrusters, even at low TRL and preliminary design stages. The framework not only accelerates design iterations but also enhances understanding of the design space, system sensitivities, and constraint interactions.

Although the current implementation relies on simplified mathematical models appropriate for PDR-level studies, the architecture is inherently modular. Higher-fidelity disciplinary models and additional propulsion subsystems can be integrated in future developments, progressively increasing the realism and predictive capability of the optimization process.

The proposed MDO framework represents a powerful and flexible tool for early-stage propulsion system design. By enabling rapid, constraint-consistent, and multidisciplinary optimization, it supports informed decision-making and technology trade-offs in the conceptual phases of spacecraft development, where design freedom is highest and system-level impact is greatest.

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